

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.24 Third Dissemination workshop results

Public

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Table of Contents

- 1. Summary..... 4
- 2. Introduction 4
- 3. 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event..... 4
 - 3.1. Main goal of the event 4
 - 3.2. Summary of the event 5
- 4. Conclusion 6
- Annex 1 Agenda of the 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination & Cybercrime Community Even 6

1. Summary

This document is a part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). The goal of the deliverable D6.24 “Third Dissemination workshop results” is to summarise the 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination & Cybercrime Community Event which was held on 16th - 17th April 2024 in Vienna, Austria.

2. Introduction

The project dissemination activities are mainly focused on network extension and sharing of the results internally and among the identified external stakeholders and audience of interest. Thus, the project should have an understandable stakeholders’ engagement approach to amplify the results and activities of other members of the cybercrime ecosystem – helping to maximise impact and positive change in the fight against different forms of cybercrime.

The CYCLOPES network stakeholder audience are defined as follows:

Audience 1: Practitioners (i.e. LEAs) interested in the uptake of security research and innovation in relation to the fight against cybercrime. All CYCLOPES partners engage practitioners throughout the project timeframe by inviting relevant stakeholders to the projects’ events and workshops, by proposing that they take part in different initiatives and ask for their feedback on how CYCLOPES solutions can support enhanced resilience to cybercrime.

Audience 2: Industry including SMEs. CYCLOPES engage industry players having interests in fighting cybercrime. This network is invited to participate in the CYCLOPES events, workshops and webinars and receives all supportive documents needed to actively participate in key activities.

Audience 3: Scientific community. CYCLOPES results and updates are delivering to the relevant EU and Member State organisations such as Universities, Research and Technology Organisations, research communities and institutes, as well as the private sector.

Audience 4: Policymakers. CYCLOPES identify and proactively contact with targeted audience and invite interested actors to the projects’ events and workshops. CYCLOPES reach policymakers on both a European (i.e. DG Home, DG Connect, DG Grow) and on Member State level.

Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient audience relations in order to enable interaction between differing innovation parties, and build synergies with already established European, and national networks of practitioners.

3. 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event

3.1. Main goal of the event

The dissemination is a fundamental activity to create project visibility and reach various target groups. Efficient dissemination during the CYCLOPES project ensures short and long-term success and through yearly Dissemination Events, CYCLOPES ensures that:

- Project outputs and outcomes are widely disseminated to the right target audiences.
- Stakeholders can contribute to the output’s development, evaluation and exploitation. Thus, they should be identified and encouraged from the beginning to proactively interact with the consortium partners on a systematic basis.

A crucial part of dissemination events is to present the main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient interaction between CYCLOPES and relevant partners. These events foster network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners and stakeholders who may wish to join to the CYCLOPES network and its activities.

3.2. Summary of the event

On the 16th and 17th April 2024, the 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination & Cybercrime Community Event took place to discuss various topics that support successful fight and prevent cybercrime. The event was hosted by the CYCLOPES partner Austrian International Standards (ASI) at the House of Standards & Innovation in Vienna where experts contribute to important standards to support the fight against cybercrime.

The audience consisted of 90 people from European law enforcement agencies, industry and science as well as relevant networks and organisations responsible for fighting cybercrime. The CYCLOPES event in Vienna aimed also to provide a platform to present the results of the European projects and other organisations and initiatives and to gather participants' needs and recommendations for future activities.

The 1st day of the event started with opening words from CYCLOPES Coordinator followed by a representative from DG-Home, who presented in the keynote lecture thoughts on enhancing law enforcement capacity and capability in digital investigations. The European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA) and the Tools4LEAs project were also presented during the morning session.

The agenda then consisted of parallel, interactive sessions to address the priorities previously obtained through CYCLOPES' practitioners' workshops. The aim was to summarize the main findings of these past practitioner workshops, and to provide an update of new developments in each respective theme. This was done by presenting a view from the CYCLOPES team, a the perspective of the end users, and invite other R&I projects to give an update of recent developments.

The event was split across specific pillars, with horizontal topics included in each day:

- Cryptocurrency
- Cloud Services
- Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearables and IoT
- Relations between cybersecurity & cybercrime
- Preventing and investigating Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation

The event included also interesting session on Artificial Intelligence in relation to fighting cybercrime, standardisation workshop and presentation of the European Cybercrime Centre (EC3) and the Europol Innovation Lab. Furthermore, the following EU funded projects presented their results: Anti-FinTer, CYBERSPACE, POLIICE, UnderServed, FORMOBILE, NOTIONES, EU-HYBNET, ENACT, STARLIGHT, ALIGNER, ECTEG - Decrypt Square project, Emerge IoT, UNVOVER, TCO Cluster (ALLIES, FRISCO, TATE), MISP-LEA, AIL, eFirst, OVERCLOCK, 00) ARICA, LEAGUE and CPORT. Each day of the event ended with concluding remarks followed by networking sessions.

4. Conclusion

This document summaries the 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination & Cybercrime Community Event which aim was not only to share the results of the CYCLOPES project but also to discuss various topics that support successful fight and prevent cybercrime.

Overall, the event was a success with insightful presentations, tool demonstrations, keynote speeches and interactive sessions. The participants used this networking event to exchange information on new methods for combating cybercrime and highlighted some of the challenges currently faced.

Annex 1 Agenda of the 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination & Cybercrime Community Even

THIRD ANNUAL DISSEMINATION EVENT AGENDA

16th April 2024 / Tuesday

08:30 - 09:30 Registration & Welcome Coffee & Networking

09:30 - 10:00 Welcoming words & Introduction to the event,
PPHS & ASI

10:00 - 10:30 DG HOME, 'Enhancing law enforcement capacity and capability in digital investigations', *Gilles Robine, DG HOME European Commission*

10:30 - 11:00 European Cybercrime Centre - EC3

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee Break & Networking

Parallel Breakout Sessions: presentations / workshops / trainings

	Main conference room Topic: Cryptocurrency Moderator: Steven Ormston, PPHS	Workshop room #1	Workshop room #2 Topic: Project Presentations
11:30 - 12:00	Introduction to the topic and practitioner presentation <i>Wesley Kenny, Garda National Cyber Crime Bureau</i>	ARICA project <i>Assessing Risk Indicators of child Sexual Abuse</i>	(11:30 - 12:00) CYBERSPACE project Enhancing cybersecurity, improving cooperation and the reporting of cyberattacks in the EU <i>Jakob Rosner, University of Applied Sciences for Public Service in Bavaria</i>
12:00 - 12:30	Anti-FinTer project Versatile artificial intelligence investigative technologies for revealing online cross-border financing activities of terrorism <i>Ross King, AIT</i>	ARICA is a two-year project funded by the European Union's Internal Security Fund, which aims to support law enforcement agencies in their fight against child sexual abuse. It develops technologies that will enhance the LEAs' capabilities in investigations on online child sexual abuse material (CSAM). These technologies will remain free to use for LEA after the end of the project. <i>Dr. Salla Huikuri, Finnish Ministry of Interior</i> Note: Session is only open for LEAs	(12:00 - 12:30) POLIICE project Powerful Lawful Interception, Investigation, and Intelligence <i>Gideon Hazzani, LibereU</i>
12:30 - 13:00	Cybertrading fraud and the need for cryptocurrency analytics <i>Stephan Schäl, Bavarian Central Office for the Prosecution of Cybercrime, Germany</i>		(12:30 - 13:00) UNDERSERVED project Empower law enforcement agencies to support humanitarian actors in cyberspace <i>Michael O'Callaghan, UCD Centre for Cybersecurity & Cybercrime Investigation</i>

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16th April 2024 / Tuesday (Cont.)

13:00 – 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 14:30	European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA) presentation, <i>Eva Škruba, EACTDA</i>

Parallel Breakout Sessions: presentations / workshops / trainings

	Main conference room Topic: Cloud Services Moderator:	Workshop room #1 Topic: EACTDA Workshop	Workshop room #2 Topic: Project Presentations
14:30 – 15:00	Introduction to the topic and practitioner presentation, <i>Hinesh Mehta, West Midlands Police, UK</i>	(14:30 - 16:00) EACTDA workshop Tools Showroom by EACTDA EACTDA/Tools4LEAs facilitates the uptake of technological solutions by EU public security practitioners fighting cybercrime. 8 tools were further developed in Tools4LEAs v1 and we have many more in the pipeline at the moment. During the hands-on session you will have an opportunity to interact with some of the Tools4LEAs tools. Note: workshop only for EU LEA.	(14:30 - 15:00) NOTIONES project Interacting network of intelligence and security practitioners with industry and academia actors <i>Alexander Nikolov, SYNNO</i>
15:00 – 15:30	FORMOBILE project From mobile phones to court – A complete FORnsic investigation chain targeting MOBILE devices <i>Prof. Dr. Dirk Pawlaszczyk, Mittweida University of Applied Sciences</i>		(15:00 - 15:30) EU-HYBNET project Empowering a Pan-European Network to Counter Hybrid Threats, <i>Tuomas Tammilehto, Laurea</i>
15:30 – 16:00	'Cloud Services in the International cooperation landscape', <i>Lukasz Matysiak, Central Cybercrime Bureau representative at J-CAT, Europol</i>		(15:30 - 16:00) ENACT project European Network Against Crime and Terrorism <i>Helen Gibson, CENTRIC</i>
16:00 – 16:10	Presentation of CYCLOPES Automotive Digital Forensics Group <i>Alexander Bijens, Belgium Federal Police</i>		
16:10 – 16:20	Closing Remarks of the 1st Day		
16:30 – 19:00	Networking Session with finger food		

17th April 2024 / Wednesday

08:30 - 09:30 Welcome Coffee & Networking

09:30 - 10:00 **EUROPOL Innovation Lab** presentation – *Marcel Patatu*

10:00 - 11:00 Session dedicated to AI in relation to fighting cybercrime **STARLIGHT & ALIGNER & CRI**
Dr. Daniel Lückerath, Fraunhofer Institute for Intelligent Analysis and Information Systems IAIS, ALIGNER project Coordinator
Prof Dr Marco Gercke, Cybercrime Research Institute (CRI)
Moderator: Freek Bomhof, TNO

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee Break & Networking

Parallel Breakout Sessions: presentations / workshops / trainings

<p>Main conference room Topic: Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearables and IoT <i>Moderator: Michael O'Callaghan, UCD CCI</i></p>	<p>Workshop room #1 Topic: EACTDA Workshop</p>	<p>Workshop room #2 Topic: Project Presentations</p>
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11:30 - 12:00 Introduction to the topic and practitioner presentation, *Johnny Bengtsson, Swedish National Forensic Centre*

12:00 - 12:30 **ECTEG - Decrypt Square Project**
Lavinia Egidi, University of Eastern Piedmont

12:30 - 13:00 **Emerge IoT project**
Dr. Enrico Seib, State Police Office for Criminal Investigation Mecklenburg Western-Pomerania

13:00 - 13:15 **UNCOVER project:**
 Development of an efficient steganalysis framework for uncovering hidden data in digital media, *David Daems, Royal Military Academy*

(11:30 - 13:15) **EACTDA** workshop
 Tools Showroom by EACTDA

(11:30 - 12:30) **TCO Cluster: ALLIES, FRISCO, TATE**
 Regulation on Terrorist Content Online (TCO)
Adeline Kugler, FRISCO project
Pierre Sivignon, FRISCO project
Andrew Staniforth, TATE project
Sophia Rothut, TATE project
Martina bogdanova, ALLIES project
Maria Lachova, ALLIES project

(12:30 - 13:15) Standardisation Workshop
Karl Grün and Jörg Nachbaur, Austrian Standards International

17th April 2024 / Wednesday (Cont.)

Parallel Breakout Sessions: presentations / workshops / trainings

13:15 – 14:15		Lunch Break		
Main conference room Topic: Relations between cybersecurity & cybercrime Moderator: Freek Bomhof, TNO		Workshop room #1 Topic: ECTEG Workshop	Workshop room #2 Topic: Preventing and investigating Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation Moderator: Steven Ormston, PPHS	
14:15 – 15:00	Introduction to the topic and practitioner presentation, <i>Paul Johnstone, An Garda Siochana, the Irish Contact Point for the EJCN</i>	(14:15 - 15:15) eFirst project workshop <i>Yves Vandermeer, ECTEG</i>	(14:15 - 16:00) ARICA, LEAGUE, CPORT , and other projects and initiatives. <i>Dr. Salla Huikuri, ARICA 15'</i>	
15:00 – 15:30	MISP-LEA project <i>Empowering Law Enforcement Agencies with MISP: Enhancing Information Sharing and Investigation</i> Gerard Wagener, Computer Incident Response Center Luxembourg (CIRCL)		<i>Martina Bogdanova, LEAGUE project 25'</i>	
15:30 - 16:00	AIL project <i>Open source framework composed of different modules to collect, crawl, dig and analyse unstructured data</i> Aurelien Thirion, Computer Incident Response Center Luxembourg (CIRCL)	(15:15-16:00) OVERCLOCK project Operational Vanguard: using Encryption Research for Criminal LOCKdown <i>Carsten Hess, Bundeskriminalamt</i>	<i>Grete Raidma, INHOPE, CPORT project Coordinator 25'</i>	
		Note: Presentation only for LEA		<i>Sparks in the Dark: United Actions Against Child Sexual Abuse &</i>
16:00 – 16:15		Closing Remarks & end of the 2nd Day		

